

1 ***Acinetobacter pollinis* sp. nov., *Acinetobacter baretiae***
2 **sp. nov., and *Acinetobacter rathckeae* sp. nov.,**
3 **isolated from floral nectar and honeybees**

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37 **Repositories:**

38 The GenBank/ENA/DDBJ accession numbers for the partial nucleotide sequences of the 16S rRNA
39 gene are indicated in Table S1 and the accession numbers for partial *rpoB* gene sequences are
40 indicated in Table S2. The whole genome shotgun projects have been deposited at
41 DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under the accession numbers VTDL000000000-VTDT000000000.

42

43 **ABSTRACT**

44 A detailed evaluation of eight bacterial isolates from floral nectar and animal visitors to flowers
45 shows evidence that they represent three novel species in the genus *Acinetobacter*. Phylogenomic
46 analysis shows the closest relatives of these new isolates are *A. apis*, *A. boissieri*, and *A. nectaris*,
47 previously described species associated with floral nectar and bees, but high genome-wide sequence
48 divergence defines these isolates as novel species. Pairwise comparisons of the average nucleotide
49 identity (ANI) of the new isolates compared to known species is extremely low (<83%), thus
50 confirming that these samples are representative of three novel *Acinetobacter* species, for which the
51 names *Acinetobacter pollinis* sp. nov., *Acinetobacter baretae* sp. nov., and *Acinetobacter rathckeae*
52 sp. nov. are proposed. The respective type strains are SCC477^T (= TSD-214^T = LMG 31655^T), B10A^T (=
53 TSD-213^T = LMG 31702^T), and EC24^T (= TSD-215^T = LMG 31703^T = DSM 111781^T).

54

55 The genus *Acinetobacter* (*Gammaproteobacteria*) is a physiologically and metabolically diverse
56 group of bacteria currently including 65 validly published and correct names, plus several other
57 tentative designations and effectively but not validly published species names
58 (<https://lpsn.dsmz.de/genus/acinetobacter>, last accessed on March 19, 2021). *Acinetobacter* species
59 are ubiquitous in natural and human-associated environments, and a substantial proportion of them
60 are associated with animal and plant hosts [e.g. 1–6].

61 Detailed analysis of a collection of 14 *Acinetobacter* strains obtained from the floral nectar of
62 Mediterranean wild plants in southern Spain led to the description of two new species, namely *A.*
63 *nectaris* and *A. boissieri* [7]. Soon thereafter, Kim et al. [8] isolated from the intestinal tract of a
64 honey bee a bacterial strain which clustered with the *A. nectaris*-*A. boissieri* clade in both 16S rRNA
65 and *rpoB* gene trees, but was nevertheless identified and described as a new species with the name
66 *Acinetobacter apis*. However, the diversity of acinetobacters associated with flowering plants and
67 their natural visitors remains mostly unknown, even when the genus *Acinetobacter* seems to rank
68 among the main bacterial inhabitants of the floral nectar of angiosperms [9–15], and the mouth and
69 digestive tract of flower-visiting hummingbirds [15] and bumblebees [16]. In this study, we explored
70 the phylogenomic affiliation and physiology of a collection of eight bacterial isolates representing
71 three new *Acinetobacter* species associated with floral nectar and animal visitors to flowers.

72

73 Isolation and Ecology

74 The eight isolates investigated in this study are listed in Table 1. Six of these isolates were obtained
75 from nectar samples of three plant species (namely *Diplacus (Mimulus) aurantiacus*, *Epilobium*
76 *canum*, and *Scrophularia californica*, two isolates from each species) collected at different locations
77 in California, USA. The other two isolates were retrieved from the mouth and gut of honey bees
78 (*Apis mellifera*) sampled on the Stanford University campus (Stanford, CA, USA). Nectar samples
79 were diluted in 500 μ L of saline solution (0.85% w/v NaCl, Merck) and a 25- μ L aliquot of each was
80 streaked on tryptone soy agar (TSA, Oxoid) [9]. Immediately after capture, honey bees were kept
81 individually in sterile containers and anaesthetized by placing them inside a polystyrene box with ice
82 for 10-15 min, after which they were allowed to feed on sugar water (20% w/v sucrose, Sigma-
83 Aldrich) and then dissected to extract their gut. Honey bee guts were immediately ground inside a
84 microtube containing 1 mL of saline solution using a disposable pellet pestle. Aliquots of the
85 remaining sugar water and homogenized gut samples (2 μ L and 10 μ L, respectively) were streaked
86 on TSA. All cultures were incubated at 25 °C for 7 days, and a colony of each phenotypically distinct
87 microbial type was picked and separately subcultured on TSA to obtain axenic cultures. All isolates
88 were stored at -20 °C in lysogeny broth (LB, Difco) containing 25% glycerol (Sigma-Aldrich).

89 Sequence analysis of the 16S rRNA gene (>1149 bp) and of two variable regions (zones 1 and 2, 861
90 bp in total) of the *rpoB* gene, which encodes the β subunit of RNA polymerase, showed that the
91 studied isolates had the highest sequence identity with members of genus *Acinetobacter* and
92 identified *A. nectaris* and *A. boissieri* as the closest relatives (Tables S1 and S2).

93

94 **Genome Features and Phylogenomic Analysis**

95 Genomic DNA was extracted from the eight isolates using the Qiagen Blood and Tissue Kit (Qiagen,
96 Hilden, Germany), according to the manufacturer's protocol for bacterial samples. Nextera skim
97 libraries were prepared using genomic DNA and run on a 2×250 paired end Rapid Run HiSEQ 2500
98 platform at the Cornell University Institute of Biotechnology Resource Center Genomics Facility.
99 Genomic sequencing and annotation resulted in high quality bacterial genomes that were submitted
100 to GenBank (VTDL00000000- VTDT00000000) (Table 2). Genomes were assembled using Discover de
101 novo (version 52488) and authenticated through comparison of the 16S rRNA gene sequence
102 isolated by BLAST from genomic assemblies to the Sanger-sequenced 16S rRNA gene from the
103 extracted DNA of each culture. These 16S rRNA gene sequences were 99.5-99.8% similar, confirming
104 that the genomic assemblies represented the isolated cultures. The N50 for the assembled contigs
105 were between 66 and 302, as calculated by the program stats.sh provided by the Joint Genomics
106 Institute (JGI, Walnut Creek, CA). The average coverage depth of the assembled *Acinetobacter*
107 genomes was 200× or greater as estimated by BBMap [18]. Genome completeness was estimated by
108 checkM [19]. All assemblies were at least 98% complete, and the majority of genomes were more
109 than 99% complete (Table 2). Using OrthoANIu [20], genome size of the isolates was found to vary
110 between 2.59 and 2.75 Mbp and GC content between 36.6 and 39.3% (Table 2).

111 Genetic similarity between the isolates investigated in this study and previously documented
112 *Acinetobacter* species was evaluated using phylogenomic analysis. A phylogenomic tree was
113 constructed by concatenating the DNA of single-copy protein-coding genes shared by the bacterial
114 isolates and those *Acinetobacter* species identified as being reference or representative sequences
115 in PATRIC (Table S3). PhyloPhlan3 identified 261 shared proteins from RAST annotations [21];
116 shared protein sequences concatenated and aligned by PhyloPhlan were used to construct a
117 phylogenomic tree using IQ-TREE [22]. Modelfinder selected the general amino-acid exchange rate
118 matrix with empirical base frequencies and two rate categories (LG+F+R2) [23] and a consensus tree
119 was constructed using 1000 bootstrap replicates. The phylogenomic analysis of the *Acinetobacter*
120 isolates resulted in three novel clades (Fig. 1). Four isolates (*Acinetobacter* sp. SCC474, SCC477^T,
121 FNA3, and FNA11) clustered near *A. nectaris* (clade I). Additionally, isolates EC115 and EC24^T formed
122 a clade (II) closely related to *A. boissieri* ANC4422^T, as did *Acinetobacter* sp. B10A^T and B5B (clade III).

123 To evaluate if the isolates in this study represent novel species, overall genome similarity was
124 evaluated using pairwise digital DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) as implemented in Jspecies (version
125 3.7.3), and pairwise average nucleotide identity (ANI) generated using orthoANIu [20]. The ANI
126 generated by orthoANIu, which was generated using the USEARCH program [24], was compared to

127 ANI based on BLAST+ and MUMmer as well as correlation indexes of tetra-nucleotide signatures as
128 implemented in JSpecies [25]. Pairwise comparisons within the proposed new clades resulted in
129 greater than 90% DDH and greater than 98% ANI [26,27]. All isolates evaluated in this study had a
130 28% or fewer DDH and an 85% or lower ANI when compared to closely related previously described
131 *Acinetobacter* species (Table 3). Pairwise comparisons found three groups of isolates that
132 represented distinct species, and for which we propose the following names: (I) *Acinetobacter*
133 *baretiae* sp. nov., including isolates B10A^T and B5B; (II) *Acinetobacter rathckeae* sp. nov., including
134 isolates EC24^T and EC115; and (III) *Acinetobacter pollinis* sp. nov., including isolates FNA11, FNA3,
135 SCC474, and SCC477^T (Table 4). Type strains were chosen from representative isolates with the most
136 complete and least contaminated genomes, which were all at least 99.3% complete (based on
137 checkM, Table 2). Notably, despite the high ANI and DDH values obtained for isolates FNA3 and
138 FNA11, SCC474 and SCC477^T, and EC24^T and EC115, which suggest a potential clonal origin, the
139 members of each of these pairs of isolates came from nectar samples obtained from different plants
140 and displayed some phenotypic differences (see below), so we finally retained all isolates listed in
141 Table 1 in our analyses.

142

143

144 **Physiology**

145 Metabolic and physiological features were assessed using the set of tests previously described for
146 the genus *Acinetobacter* [28] (Table 4). Assimilation tests were performed in liquid basal mineral
147 medium [29] supplemented with 0.1% (w/v) of nutrient source. Temperature growth tests were
148 carried out in tryptone soy broth (TSB, Oxoid). Salt tolerance was determined by culturing isolates on
149 LB agar (Difco) containing 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10% NaCl (w/v). The ability to grow in the presence of
150 sucrose was determined by culturing the studied isolates in glass tubes containing 5 ml of LB broth
151 (Difco) supplemented with 0, 10, 20, 30, 40 or 50% sucrose (w/v, Sigma–Aldrich). Except for the
152 temperature growth tests, the incubation temperature was 25 °C. All tests were carried out in
153 duplicate on different days and results were observed after three, six and ten days of incubation.
154 Gram-staining and tests for oxidase, catalase, growth in anaerobiosis and microaerobiosis,
155 haemolysis, gelatinase and acid production from sugars were performed as detailed in Álvarez-Pérez
156 et al. [7].

157 All tested isolates were catalase positive, oxidase negative, non-hemolytic, and grew well under
158 microaerobic as well as aerobic conditions, but not in anaerobiosis. Growth was observed on TSB at

159 25 °C and 30 °C, but some isolates were able to grow at 12 °C and/or 37 °C. Isolates of *A. pollinis* and
160 *A. rathckea* tolerated sucrose concentrations up to 40%, and *A. rathckea* EC115 and some strains
161 of *A. nectaris* could even grow at 50% sucrose. None of the isolates of *A. baretiae* showed growth in
162 media containing 0% or ≥30% sucrose, and isolate B10A^T only tolerated 10% sucrose. In addition, all
163 isolates could grow in LB agar containing 0% and 1% NaCl. All *A. pollinis* isolates except SCC474 and
164 the type strain of *A. nectaris* also tolerated 3% NaCl, but none of the tested isolates grew in media
165 containing ≥5% NaCl.

166 Like their close phylogenetic relatives *A. nectaris* and *A. boissieri*, all isolates of the new species here
167 described except *A. pollinis* SCC474 assimilated fructose. Furthermore, *A. nectaris* and four of the
168 five isolates of *A. pollinis* assimilated sucrose, whereas *A. boissieri*, *A. pollinis* isolate SCC474, and all
169 the isolates of *A. baretiae* and *A. rathckea* could not grow on this carbon source. With the
170 exception of *A. baretiae* and *A. rathckea*, which only seem to grow on fructose, the isolates
171 described here tested positive in other assimilation assays. The results for these and the other
172 phenotypic analyses are summarized in Table 4.

173 Finally, we noticed some discrepancies between the results obtained in this study for assimilation of
174 some sugars and those previously obtained for the type strains of *A. nectaris* and *A. boissieri* using
175 Biolog's phenotype microarray (PM) technology, which tests for oxidation of carbon sources [7]. In
176 particular, the type strain of *A. nectaris* cannot oxidize but seems to assimilate D-glucose, a
177 discrepancy which may be due to the stringent criteria used in the interpretation of PM profiles (e.g.,
178 reactions were considered positive only if the net area under the curve exceeded 5000 units, and no
179 cutoff values for "weak positive" reactions were set [7]). On the other hand, the type strain of *A.*
180 *boissieri* can oxidize but does not seem to assimilate sucrose. It should be taken into account that
181 Biolog's PM technology detects metabolic activity through production of NADH that engenders a
182 redox potential and flow of electrons to reduce a tetrazolium dye [30], rather than actual substrate
183 consumption. Therefore, this PM technology does not necessarily yield the same results as
184 assimilation assays.

185

186 **Description of *Acinetobacter pollinis* sp. nov.**

187 *Acinetobacter pollinis* [pol.li'nis. L. gen. n. *pollinis* of pollen, because isolates are often obtained from
188 pollen as well as nectar [31]].

189 The description is based on the characteristics of four isolates from the floral nectar of *Diplacus*
190 (*Mimulus*) *aurantiacus* and *Scrophularia californica* plants collected in California, USA (isolates FNA3,
191 FNA11, SCC474, SCC477^T). Cells are Gram-negative, aerobic, oxidase-negative, catalase-positive,
192 non-motile coccobacilli, generally occurring in pairs. All isolates tested can grow at decreased oxygen
193 concentrations, but not under anaerobic conditions. Growth occurs at 12, 25, 30, and 37 °C, but not
194 at 4 and 41 °C. Colonies on TSA medium are round and smooth, raised or slightly umbonate, cream,
195 slightly opaque, with entire margins and 1–6 mm in diameter after 4 days of incubation at 25 °C.
196 Growth is observed on Columbia agar supplemented with sheep blood, but all isolates are non-
197 hemolytic on this medium. All isolates are negative for gelatin hydrolysis and utilization of Simmons'
198 citrate, and positive for D-fructose, D-glucose and sucrose acidification. The only carbon source
199 assimilated by all isolates tested is 4-aminobutyrate. Variable results were observed for L-aspartate,
200 D-fructose, L-glutamate and sucrose (negative for SCC474, positive for the rest), and D-gluconate
201 and D-glucose (negative for SCC474 and SCC477^T, positive for the rest). No growth occurs on acetate,
202 trans-aconitate, adipate, β-alanine, L-arabinose, L-arginine, azelate, benzoate, 2,3-butanediol,
203 citraconate, ethanol, gentisate, glutarate, histamine, L-histidine, 4-hydroxybenzoate, DL-lactate, L-
204 leucine, levulinate, D-malate, malonate, L-ornithine, phenylacetate, L-phenylalanine, putrescine, D-
205 ribose, L-tartrate, tricarballoylate, trigonelline, and tryptamine. Sucrose is tolerated at concentrations
206 ranging from 0% to 40% (w/v). Growth occurs in media containing 0% and 1% NaCl (w/v) and all
207 tested isolates except SCC474 also grow in LB agar supplemented with 3% NaCl.

208 The type strain SCC477^T (= TSD-214^T = LMG 31655^T) was isolated from the floral nectar of a
209 *Scrophularia californica* (California figwort) plant collected at Stebbins Cold Canyon Reserve (CA,
210 USA). The genome size of the isolates tested ranged from 2.67 to 2.76 Mb (2.75 Mb for the type
211 strain) with GC content of 36.6-36.7 mol%.

212 The genome assemblies, 16S rRNA and *rpoB* gene sequences corresponding to the four tested
213 isolates have been deposited in the GenBank/EMBL/ DDBJ data bases under the following accession
214 numbers: GCA_015627175.1, MN701878 and MN389214 for SCC477^T; GCA_015627215.1,
215 MN701875 and MN315325 for FNA3; GCA_015627205.1, MN701874 and MN315322 for FNA11; and
216 GCA_015627235.1, MN701877 and MN389213 for SCC474.

217 **Description of *Acinetobacter rathckeae* sp. nov.**

218 *Acinetobacter rathckeae* [rath.cke'ae. N.L. gen. fem. n. *rathckeae* of Rathcke, named after the
219 American evolutionary ecologist Beverly Rathcke (1945–2011), in recognition of her contribution to
220 pollination ecology].

221 The description is based on the characteristics of two isolates (EC24^T and EC115) which were isolated
222 from the floral nectar of *Epilobium canum* plants in California, USA. Cells are Gram-negative, aerobic,
223 oxidase-negative, catalase-positive, non-motile coccobacilli. The isolates tested can grow at
224 decreased oxygen concentrations, but not under anaerobic conditions. Growth occurs at 25 and 30
225 °C, but not at 4, 37 and 41 °C. Only one of the two isolates (EC115) can grow at 12 °C. Colonies on
226 TSA medium are round and smooth, flat, white-cream, with entire margins and <1–2 mm in
227 diameter after 4 days of incubation at 25 °C. Growth is observed on Columbia agar supplemented
228 with sheep blood, but the isolates are non-hemolytic on this medium. Both isolates are negative for
229 gelatin hydrolysis and utilization of Simmons' citrate, and positive for D-fructose, D-glucose and
230 sucrose acidification. The only carbon source assimilated by the two isolates tested is D-fructose. No
231 growth occurs on acetate, trans-aconitate, adipate, β-alanine, 4-aminobutyrate, L-arabinose, L-
232 arginine, L-aspartate, azelate, benzoate, 2,3-butanediol, citraconate, ethanol, gentisate, D-
233 gluconate, D-glucose, L-glutamate, glutarate, histamine, L-histidine, 4-hydroxybenzoate, DL-lactate,
234 L-leucine, levulinate, D-malate, malonate, L-ornithine, phenylacetate, L-phenylalanine, putrescine, D-
235 ribose, sucrose, L-tartrate, tricarballoylate, trigonelline, and tryptamine. Sucrose is tolerated at
236 concentrations ranging from 0% to 40% (w/v), and isolate EC115 also grows at 50% sucrose. Growth
237 occurs in media containing 0% and 1% NaCl (w/v), but not ≥3% NaCl.

238 The type strain EC24^T (= TSD-215^T = LMG 31703^T = DSM 111781^T) was isolated from the floral nectar
239 of an *E. canum* (California fuchsia) plant collected at UC Davis campus (Davis, CA, USA). The genome
240 size is 2.75 Mb for EC24^T and 2.62 Mb for EC115 (= DSM 111782), with GC content of 39.3 and 39.2
241 mol%, respectively.

242 The genome assemblies, 16S rRNA and *rpoB* gene sequences corresponding to these isolates have
243 been deposited in the GenBank/EMBL/ DDBJ data bases under the following accession numbers:
244 GCA_015627125.1, MN701873 and MN389216 for EC24^T; and GCA_015627165.1, MN701872 and
245 MN389215 for EC115.

246

247 **Description of *Acinetobacter baretiae* sp. nov.**

248 *Acinetobacter baretiae* [ba.re'ti.æ N.L. gen. fem. n. *baretiae* of Baret, named after the French
249 botanist Jeanne Baret (1740–1807), in recognition of her contribution to botanical expeditions and
250 her pioneering role as a female explorer and scientist].

251 The description is based on the characteristics of two isolates (B5B and B10A^T) obtained from the
252 mouth and midgut of honey bees, *Apis mellifera*, collected in the Merck Green, located between the
253 Gilbert Building and the Herrin Laboratories on the Stanford University campus in Stanford, CA, USA.
254 Cells are Gram-negative, aerobic, oxidase-negative, catalase-positive, non-motile coccobacilli. The
255 isolates tested can grow at decreased oxygen concentrations, but not under anaerobic conditions.
256 Growth occurs at 12, 25 and 30 °C, but not at 4, 37 and 41 °C. Colonies on TSA medium are round,
257 smooth, flat or slightly umbonate, white, slightly opaque, with entire margins and <1–2 mm in
258 diameter after 4 days of incubation at 25 °C. Growth is observed on Columbia agar supplemented
259 with sheep blood, but the isolates are non-hemolytic on this medium. Both isolates are negative for
260 gelatin hydrolysis and utilization of Simmons' citrate, and positive for D-fructose, D-glucose and
261 sucrose acidification. The only carbon source assimilated by the two isolates tested is D-fructose. No
262 growth occurs on acetate, trans-aconitate, adipate, β-alanine, 4-aminobutyrate, L-arabinose, L-
263 arginine, L-aspartate, azelate, benzoate, 2,3-butanediol, citraconate, ethanol, gentisate, D-
264 gluconate, D-glucose, L-glutamate, glutarate, histamine, L-histidine, 4-hydroxybenzoate, DL-lactate,
265 L-leucine, levulinate, D-malate, malonate, L-ornithine, phenylacetate, L-phenylalanine, putrescine, D-
266 ribose, sucrose, L-tartrate, tricarballylate, trigonelline, and tryptamine. Sucrose is tolerated at 10%
267 (w/v, both isolates) and 20% (only isolate B5B), and tested isolates failed to grow in LB broth
268 containing no sucrose. Growth occurs in media containing 0% and 1% NaCl (w/v), but not ≥3% NaCl.

269 The type strain B10A^T (= TSD-213^T = LMG 31702^T) was isolated from the gut of an *A. mellifera* (honey
270 bee) individual sampled at Stanford campus (Stanford, CA, USA). The genome size is 2.70 Mb for
271 B10A^T and 2.59 Mb for B5B, with GC content of 37.5 mol% for both isolates.

272 The genome assemblies, 16S rRNA and *rpoB* gene sequences corresponding to these isolates have
273 been deposited in the GenBank/EMBL/ DDBJ data bases under the following accession numbers:
274 GCA_015627105.1, MN709041 and MN315286 for B10AT; and GCA_015627115.1, MN701871 and
275 MN315310 for B5B.

276

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279 Conceptualization and resources: all authors.

280 Investigation, formal analysis and data curation: SA-P, LJB and VAS.

281 Writing – Original Draft Preparation: SA-P, LJB, RLV, BL and TAH.

282 Writing – Review and Editing: all authors.

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286 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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304 **ABBREVIATIONS**

305 ANI: average nucleotide identity

306 DDH: DNA-DNA hybridization

307 LB: lysogeny broth

308 TSA: tryptone soy agar

309 TSB: tryptone soy broth

310

311

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399

400 **FIGURES AND TABLES**

401 **Figure 1:** Maximum-likelihood phylogenomic tree constructed from shared concatenated RAST
402 proteins identified by PhyloPHLan3 and constructed using IQTREE. The proposed new species are
403 delineated by grey markings within the tree and numbered clades. The tree was constructed using
404 the general time reversible model and bootstrap values based on 1000 replicates are listed at nodes.

405

Taxonomic Description

406 **Table 1:** Overview of the *Acinetobacter* isolates analyzed in this study.

Species	Isolate	Source	Sampling location	Year of isolation	Isolate donor*
<i>Acinetobacter pollinis</i> sp. nov.	FNA3	Floral nectar of <i>Diplacus (Mimulus) aurantiacus</i> (Phrymaceae)	Jasper Ridge Biological Preserve, Stanford (California, USA)	2017	KT, TF
	FNA11	Floral nectar of <i>Diplacus (Mimulus) aurantiacus</i> (Phrymaceae)	Jasper Ridge Biological Preserve, Stanford (California, USA)	2017	KT, TF
	SCC474	Floral nectar of <i>Scrophularia californica</i> (Scrophulariaceae)	Stebbins Cold Canyon Reserve (California, USA)	2016	RV, GH
	SCC477 ^T	Floral nectar of <i>Scrophularia californica</i> (Scrophulariaceae)	Stebbins Cold Canyon Reserve (California, USA)	2016	RV, GH
<i>Acinetobacter rathckeae</i> sp. nov.	EC115	Floral nectar of <i>Epilobium canum</i> (Onagraceae)	UC Davis campus (California, USA)	2015	RV, MM
	EC24 ^T	Floral nectar of <i>Epilobium canum</i> (Onagraceae)	UC Davis campus (California, USA)	2015	RV, MM
<i>Acinetobacter baretiae</i> sp. nov.	B10A ^T	Gut of <i>Apis mellifera</i>	Stanford campus (California, USA)	2018	TF, SAP
	B5B	Mouthparts of <i>Apis mellifera</i>	Stanford campus (California, USA)	2018	TF, SAP

407

408 * Isolate donors: GH, Griffin Hall (UC Davis, USA); KT, Kaoru Tsuji (Center for Ecological Research-Kyoto University, Japan); MM, Megan Morris (Stanford University, USA);
409 RV, Rachel Vannette (UC Davis, USA); SAP, Sergio Álvarez-Pérez (KU Leuven, Belgium); TF, Tadashi Fukami (Stanford University, USA).

410 **Table 2:** Genome characteristics of the *Acinetobacter* isolates investigated in this study. Genome size, GC content, and contig number was assessed by
 411 ORthoANlu, N50 was estimated by stats.sh in JGI, and coverage was as generated by BBMap and completeness was estimated by checkM. 16S rRNA gene
 412 similarity between genomic and Sanger sequencing efforts was generated using BLAST.

Isolate	Size (Mb)	GC content (%)	Contigs (#)	N50 (Kb)	Ave coverage	Stdev coverage	Complete (%)	16S similarity
<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov. B10A ^T	2.70	37.5	64	104	799	412	99.9	99.6
<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov. B5B	2.59	37.5	68	96	830	497	99.5	99.6
<i>A. rathckeae</i> sp. nov. EC115	2.62	39.2	25	208	461	1397	99.3	99.8
<i>A. rathckeae</i> sp. nov. EC24 ^T	2.75	39.3	17	302	407	1586	99.9	99.8
<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. FNA11	2.67	36.6	75	117	1223	573	99.9	99.6
<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. FNA3	2.67	36.6	84	97	865	9520	99.3	99.5
<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. SCC474	2.75	36.7	127	71	216	417	98.1	99.9
<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. SCC477 ^T	2.75	36.7	90	66	274	599	99.3	99.7

413

414

Taxonomic Description

415

416 **Table 3:** Digital DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) (Jspecies) and pairwise average nucleotide identity
 417 (ANI) (orthoANIu) for the isolates used in this study and closely related *Acinetobacter* species. DDH
 418 values greater than 70% and ANI values greater than 96% denote the pair are the same species and
 419 are highlighted in light grey (DDH) and dark grey (ANI); species groupings are labeled.

	I				II				III				
	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. FNA3	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. FNA11	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. SCC474	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. SCC477 ¹	<i>A. rathckeae</i> sp. nov. EC24 ¹	<i>A. rathckeae</i> sp. nov. EC115	<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov. B5B	<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov. B10A ¹	<i>A. apis</i> ANC 5514	<i>A. boissieri</i> ANC 4422	<i>A. nectaris</i> CIP 110549	<i>A. brisouii</i> ANC 4119 ^T	
I	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. FNA3	100.0	97.0	97.0	20.1	19.7	19.9	20.1	20.0	19.1	19.3	24.6	DDH
	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. FNA11	100.0	97.0	97.1	20.1	19.7	20.0	20.1	19.1	19.3	24.5	20.0	
	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. SCC474	99.7	99.7	99.9	19.6	19.8	20.0	20.0	19.1	19.4	24.7	20.1	
	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov. SCC477 ¹	99.6	99.7	100.0	19.6	19.8	19.9	19.9	19.0	19.4	24.6	20.1	
II	<i>A. rathckeae</i> sp. nov. EC24 ¹	75.3	75.0	74.8	74.6	98.1	23.6	23.5	19.6	28.4	20.4	19.9	
	<i>A. rathckeae</i> sp. nov. EC115	74.7	82.1	74.7	74.6	99.7	24.1	23.5	19.6	28.4	20.0	20.0	
III	<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov. B5B	74.6	74.6	74.4	74.4	81.2	81.8	94.4	19.5	23.9	19.7	19.9	
	<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov. B10A ¹	74.7	74.6	74.4	74.8	81.2	81.3	99.3	19.5	23.9	19.7	20.0	
	<i>A. apis</i> ANC 5514	74.8	74.7	74.4	74.3	74.1	74.5	73.1	73.5				
	<i>A. boissieri</i> ANC 4422	84.7	84.9	74.8	74.4	74.6	74.5	73.3	73.2				
	<i>A. nectaris</i> CIP 110549	75.2	75.5	82.0	82.1	82.4	82.2	73.4	73.7				
	<i>A. brisouii</i> ANC 4119 ^T	73.1	73.0	73.2	73.3	73.3	73.2	75.9	75.8				

ANI

420

421

Taxonomic Description

422 **Table 4:** Metabolic and physiological characteristics of the *Acinetobacter* isolates included in this study in comparison with their closest phylogenetic
423 relatives.*

	<i>A. pollinis</i> sp. nov.				<i>A. rathckeeae</i> sp. nov.		<i>A. barettiae</i> sp. nov.		<i>A. nectarist</i> [†]		<i>A. boissierit</i> [†]		<i>A. apis</i>
Characteristic	FNA3	FNA11	SCC474	SCC477 [†]	EC24 [†]	EC115	B10A [†]	B5B	SAP 763.2 [†]	Other isolates [‡]	SAP 284.1 [†]	Other isolates [‡]	HYN18 [†]
Growth on TSB at:													
4°C	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	w	+	–
12°C	+	+	+	+	–	+	+	+	+	ND	w	ND	ND
25°C	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
30°C	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
37°C	+	+	+	+	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
41°C	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Acid from sucrose	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND
Acid from glucose	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Acid from fructose	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND	+	ND	ND
Citrate (Simmons)	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	ND	–	ND	+

Growth on LB agar plus NaCl at:													
0% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND	+	ND	+
1% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND	+	ND	+
3% (w/v)	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	ND	-	ND	-
5% (w/v)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
7.5% (w/v)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
10% (w/v)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
Growth on LB broth plus sucrose at:													
0% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	ND
10% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	ND
20% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	ND
30% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	w	w	ND
40% (w/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	w	w	ND
50% (w/v)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	w	+	w	w	ND
Assimilation of:													
Acetate	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-(-)	(-)	-(-)	(-)	-
4-Aminobutyrate	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	ND	-	ND	-
L-Arabinose	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-(-)	(-)	-(-)	(-)	-
L-Aspartate	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+(+)	(+)	-(-)	(-)	-

2,3-Butanediol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
Ethanol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
D-Gluconate	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+ (+)	(v)	- (-)	(-)	+
D-Glucose	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+ (-)	(v)	- (-)	(-)	+
L-Glutamate	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+ (+)	(+)	- (-)	(v)	+
DL-Lactate	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
Phenylacetate	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
D-Ribose	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	- (-)	-	- (-)	-	-
Trigonelline	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ND	-	ND	-
Sucrose	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+ (+)	(+)	- (+)	(+)	ND
D-Fructose	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+ (+)	(+)	+ (+)	(+)	ND

424

425 *All tested isolates were positive for catalase production and growth in microaerobiosis, and negative for oxidase and gelatinase production, haemolysis
426 and growth in anaerobiosis. Furthermore, all isolates tested negative for assimilation of the following nutrient sources: *trans*-aconitate, adipate, β -alanine,
427 L-arginine, azelate, benzoate, citraconate, gentisate, glutarate, histamine, L-histidine, 4-hydroxybenzoate, L-leucine, levulinate, D-malate, malonate, L-
428 ornithine, L-phenylalanine, putrescine, L-tartrate, tricarallylate, and tryptamine. +, positive reaction; -, negative reaction; w, weak growth; v, variable
429 results; ND, not determined.

430 †Results shown in parentheses refer to oxidation of carbon sources, as determined in a previous study using Phenotype MicroArray (PM) technology (see
431 Ref. [7]). Note the discrepancies observed between assimilation and oxidation of D- glucose and sucrose for the type strains of *A. nectaris* and *A. boissieri*,
432 respectively.

433 ‡Results obtained by Álvarez-Pérez *et al.* [7] for other conspecific isolates.